

Comparative studies in anionic, cationic and nonionic surfactants in photogalvanic cells from solar energy conversion and storage point of view : NTA-Azur B system

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The photogalvanic effect was studied in photogalvanic cell containing nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA) as a reductant, Azur B as a photosensitizer and sodium lauryl sulphate (anionic), cetyl pyridinium chloride (cationic) and Tween 80 (nonionic) as surfactant from solar energy conversion and storage point of view. The conversion efficiency for anionic, cationic and nonionic surfactants above their cmc were 0.4053, 0.1386 and 0.2177% and storage capacity 105, 31 and 74 min respectively. The effect of variations of various parameters on electrical output and *i*-*V* characteristics of the cell were observed and a mechanism for generation of photocurrent has also been proposed.

Recently we have reported some photogalvanic systems with reasonably good amount of electrical output and storage capacity¹. The photogalvanic effect still in infant stage and requires thorough exploration to achieve the higher conversion efficiency as well as commercial viability. In order to reach a point of satisfaction the efforts are being made by adding surfactants in the photogalvanic cells and selecting cheaper substances.

Now, it is worthwhile to interpret the observations to arrive at satisfactory mechanism of photocurrent generation, cell performance, conversion efficiency of the cell and to decide the role of various type of micelles in photogalvanic cell.

Results and discussion

On illumination, the system consisting of Azur B-NTA generates photovoltage and photocurrent in aqueous medium into and without surfactant. These photovoltage and photocurrent have been found to change with pH of the solution and the optimum condition is in the alkaline range (pH = 11.6–13.8).

The open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) and short circuit current (i_{sc}) of all these systems consisting of Azur B-NTA surfactant were measured with the help of a digital pH meter (keeping the other circuit open) and from a microammeter (keeping the other circuit closed), respectively. The electrical parameters in between these two extreme values (V_{oc}) and i_{sc}) were determined with the help of a carbon pot (log 500 K) connected in the circuit of microammeter through

which an external load in the circuit was applied and results are summarized in Table 1. It was observed that in all these cases, *i*-*V* curves deviated from their expected regular rectangular shape. The power point (a point on the curve where the product of potential and current is maximum) in these *i*-*V* curves were determined and their fill factor (*n*) were also calculated using relation :

$$n = \frac{V_{pp} \times i_{pp}}{V_{oc} \times i_{sc}}$$

On the basis of fill factor calculated, the order of the efficiency of photogalvanic cells in the presence of surfactant was : anionic (NaLS) > nonionic (Tween 80) > without surfactant > cationic (CPC) surfactant.

The performance (storage capacity) of the photogalvanic cells containing Azur B-NTA system in three types of surfactant were studied by applying the desired external load to have the potential and current corresponding to power point, after removing the source of illumination. It was quite interesting to observe that the performance of the cell in dark was affected appreciably in the presence of surfactants. A comparison of performance is given in Table 1 and the order of performance of these cells in dark in presence of various types of surfactant was as follows : anionic (NaLS) > nonionic (Tween 80) > without surfactant > cationic (CPC) surfactant.

The conversion efficiency of all these photogalvanic systems were calculated using the electrical output at power point and the power of incident radiations. The systems (at

Note

Table 1. Characteristics of the photogalvanic cells

[NaLS] = 6.0×10^{-3} M, [Azur B] = 9.6×10^{-5} M, (Tween 80) = 2.0×10^{-3} M, [NTA] = 2.0×10^{-2} M, [CPC] = 5.6×10^{-4} M, light intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2} , temp. = 303 K

System	V_{oc} mV	i_{sc} μA	V_{pp} mV	i_{pp} μA	n
Azur B-NTA-NaLS	811.00	140.00	527.00	80.00	0.37
Azur B-NTA-Tween 80	729.00	95.00	453.00	50.00	0.32
Azur B-NTA-CPC	718.00	65.00	412.00	35.00	0.30
Azur B-NTA-without surfactant	996.00	70.00	701.00	25.00	0.25

Surfactants	Power μW	$t/2$ min
Anionic micelle (NaLS)	42.16	105.0
Nonionic micelle (Tween 80)	22.65	74.0
Cationic-micelle (CPC)	14.42	31.0
Without micelle	17.52	12.0

Surfactants	Conversion efficiency %	Sunlight conversion data	
		Photopotential mV	Photocurrent μA
Anionic micelle (NaLS)	0.4053	738.0	128.0
Nonionic micelle (Tween 80)	0.2177	589.0	750.0
Cationic micelle (CPC)	0.1386	577.0	560.0
Without micelle	0.1685	841.0	300.0

their optimum conditions) were also exposed to sunlight. The conversion efficiency and sunlight conversion data for these photogalvanic cells are reported in Table 1. On the basis of observed data, the photogalvanic cells containing different type of surfactants have the decreasing efficiency in the order : anionic (NaLS) > nonionic (Tween 80) > without surfactant > cationic (CPC) surfactant.

On the basis of these observations, a tentative mechanism has also been proposed for the generation of photocurrent in these photogalvanic cells as :

Illuminated chamber :

On irradiation dye molecules get excited form

The excited dye molecules (AB^*) accept electrons from reductant (R) and electroactive species are generated. These electroactive species react at the light and counter dark electrode to generate current.

Thus the photogalvanic cell containing dye and reductant

absorbs photon energy and this energy is converted into electrical energy by electrode reaction through the formation of excited state of electron donor acceptor type.

Conclusions :

On the basis of observed data, the photogalvanic cells containing Azur B-NTA-surfactant system, the anionic (NaLS), was the most suitable surfactant to be used in these cells from conversion efficiency and storage capacity point of view and these are competently followed by systems containing nonionic and cationic surfactant but are with value ranging 1.5–2.0 times less than the anionic surfactant containing Azur B-NTA in photogalvanic cells. The photogalvanic cells containing anionic surfactant (sodium lauryl sulphate) show very high storage capacity i.e. can work for 105 min in dark and are efficient for solar energy conversion.

Experimental

Nitrilotriacetic acid (Sigma), Azur B (s.d. fine), sodium lauryl sulphate (Sisco), Tween 80 (Sisco), cetyl pyridinium chloride (Loba) and sodium hydroxide (s.d. fine) were used in the present work. All the solutions were prepared in double-distilled water and were kept in amber coloured containers. Concentrations of surfactants NaLS, Tween 80 and

CPC were 6.0×10^{-3} , 2.0×10^{-3} and 5.6×10^{-4} M, respectively. A mixture of solution of the dye (Azur B), reductant (NTA), micelle (NaLS, CPC or Tween 80) and sodium hydroxide was placed in a H-type glass tube. A platinum electrode ($1.0 \times 1.0 \text{ cm}^2$) placed in one limb of the H-tube and saturated calomel electrode (SCE) in the other limb of the H-tube. The whole system was first placed in dark till a stable potential was attained, then the limb containing platinum electrode was exposed to a 200 W tungsten lamp and the limb containing SCE was kept in dark. A water filter was placed between the exposed limb and the light source to cut off infra-red radiations.

The photochemical bleaching of dye (Azur B) was studied potentiometrically. An Agronic 511 pH meter and OSAW microammeter were used to measure the potential and current generated by the system, respectively. The cur-

rent voltage characteristics were determined by applying external load with the help of carbon pot (log 500 K) connected in the circuit. The effect of variation of different parameters on electrical parameters was studied in detail.

References

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